

Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

TURNkey

Deliverable D1.2

State-of-the-art review of current EEW/OEF/RRE systems and their application to DRR planning for improved community resilience to earthquake events

Author(s):	Keith Jones, Mariantonietta Morga
Responsible Partner:	ARU
Reviewers:	John Douglas, Johannes Schweitzer, Barbara Borzi
Version:	1.0
Date:	29.11.2019
Distribution level:	Public

DOCUMENT REVISION HISTORY

Date	Version	Editor	Comments
29/11/2019	1.0	Final Draft	Final

LIST OF PARTNERS

Participant	Name	Country
NOR	Stiftelsen NORSAR	Norway
DEL	Stichting Deltares	Netherlands
KNMI	Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut	Netherlands
BRGM	Bureau de Recherches Géologiques et Minières	France
EMSC	Euro-Mediterranean Seismological Centre	France
UIce	Haskoli Islands (University of Iceland)	Iceland
EUC	Fondazione Eucentre	Italy
UStr	University of Strathclyde	UK
BUW	Bauhaus-Universität Weimar	Germany
UA	Universidad de Alicante	Spain
ARU	Anglia Ruskin University Higher Education Corporation	UK
UNIBG	Università degli Studi di Bergamo	Italy
UCL	University College London	UK
INFP	Institutul National de Cercetare si Dezvoltare pentru Fizica Pamantului	Romania
YET	YetItMoves S.r.l.	Italy
GMP	Gempa GmbH	Germany
NOA	National Observatory of Athens	Greece
NTC	Nutcracker Research Ltd.	UK
B80	Beta 80 SpA	Italy
Sim	Siminn hf.	Iceland
UPat	Panepistimio Patron (University of Patras)	Greece

GLOSSARY

Acronym	Description
EEW	Earthquake Early Warning
EIL	Earthquake Induced Liquefaction
FWCR	Forecasting – Early Warning – Consequence Prediction and Response Platform
OEF	Operational Earthquake Forecasting
PEER	Pacific Earthquake Engineering Research Centre
RAIF	Resilience Assessment and Improvement Framework
RRE	Rapid Response to Earthquakes

INDEX OF CONTENTS

Document Revision History	ii
List of Partners	ii
Glossary	ii
Index of contents	iii
Index of figures.....	iv
Index of tables	iv
1 Introduction	1
2 Background and Context to the TURNkey Project	1
3 Socio-economic-political Review of Existing Earthquake Early Warning (EEW) Systems	2
4 Socio-economic-political review of operational earthquake forecasting (OEF) systems.....	19
5 Socio-economic-political review of rapid response to earthquakes (RRE) systems	24
6 Review of the factors affecting organisation and community resilience to earthquake events	26
7 SWOT Analysis.....	30
8 summary and next steps.....	34
9 References	35

INDEX OF FIGURES

- 2 Figure 2.1: Illustration of the chronological sequence of OEF, EEW and RRE (*source: extracted from TURNkey project proposal*)
- 5 Figure 3.1: The JMA scale (*source: DOI, 2011*)
- 10 Figure 3.2: Primary and secondary benefits associated with potential application areas and impact on potential organisational benefits (*source: Table 4 PEER report number 2016/06*)
- 12 Figure 3.3: Integrated view of Telecommunications, Electricity Utility, and Information Technology Sectors in the Functionality of an EEW system and its Key Sectors and Society as a Whole (*source: PEER, 2016*)
- 25 Figure 5.1: Critical Incidents Stress Model (*source: Paton & Johnston, 2016*)
- 28 Figure 6.1: Schematic representation of the disaster resilience of place (DROP) model (*source: Cutter et al., 2008*)
- 29 Figure 6.2: LIQUEFACT tools mapped onto Cutter et al.'s DROP Model
- 30 Figure 6.3: Resilience Assessment and Improvement Framework (*source: the LIQUEFACT project*)

INDEX OF TABLES

- 14 Table 3.1: Review of perceived benefits/application issues for EEW systems
- 22 Table 4.1: Review of perceived benefits/application issues for OEF systems
- 26 Table 6.1: Characteristics/factors known to affect community resilience and how these are observed/expressed within a community (adapted from Jones, 2016)
- 31 Table 7.1: Strengths and opportunities of EEW systems to disaster risk reduction planning for improved community resilience to earthquake events
- 33 Table 7.2: Strengths and opportunities of OEF systems to disaster risk reduction planning for improved community resilience to earthquake events
- 34 Table 7.3: The theoretical/potential relationship between EEW/OEF systems and the factors influencing community resilience to earthquake events

1 INTRODUCTION

The aim of this report is to review the benefits associated with Earthquake Early Warning (EEW), Operational Earthquake Forecasting (OEF) and Rapid Response to Earthquakes (RRE) systems and provide an overview of the theory of community resilience to identify how these benefits could inform the future development of the TURNkey FWCR (Forecasting, Early Warning, Consequence prediction, Response) platform. To this end the report:

- Presents the background and context to the TURNkey project;
- Reviews the factors that affect organisational and community resilience to earthquake events, including identifying frameworks and models that link organisational and community resilience to disaster risk reduction;
- Explores the socio-economic-political benefits that could be realised from EEW, OEF and RRE systems;
- explores the socio-economic-political challenges associated with developing EEW, OEF and RRE systems;
- Identifies the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats of EEW, OEF and RRE systems and maps these against the needs of the different end-user stakeholder groups that will be examined in detail across the TURNkey Testbeds;
- Identifies the theoretical/potential relationships between EEW, OEF and RRE systems and the factors that influence improved community resilience to earthquake events; and
- Summarises the key issues that need to be considered by the TURNkey project partners as they develop and validate the prototype FWRC platform.

The review presented in the report should be considered a work in progress which will be amended and modified throughout the TURNkey project to reflect emerging issues identified through the participatory action research programme.

2 BACKGROUND AND CONTEXT TO THE TURNKEY PROJECT

Earthquakes are one of the most destructive natural phenomena. In the 20th century earthquakes were responsible for 1.87 million deaths and approximately \$2.935 trillion (adjusted to 2012) total economic losses (Daniell et al., 2019). Between 1980 and 2009 earthquakes affected approximately 61.5 million people worldwide, resulting in approximately 400,000 fatalities and leaving at least 16 million people homeless (Doocy et al., 2013).

A large part of Europe is at risk from earthquake disaster events; with the most seismically active areas being located in Italy, Greece, Turkey (ePACT, 2019) whilst France, Romania, The Netherlands, Cyprus and Portugal are also at risk. Over the past decade earthquakes proved to be amongst the most devastating of all European disasters, with almost 19,000 fatalities and direct economic losses of approximately €29 billion (ibid).

Although there is increased risk awareness of earthquake events amongst European citizens and policymakers, there is limited support available to help mitigate these risks. The TURNkey project seeks to address this shortcoming by developing a Forecasting - Early Warning - Consequence Prediction and Response (FWCR) platform based on a multi-sensor earthquake information system. In developing the FWCR platform TURNkey will take advantage of the latest developments in OEF and EEW systems and their use in real-time (during an event) and in near real-time, to support RRE

interventions. Whilst EEW and OEF systems are still in their infancy, particularly in Europe, their potential benefits to society and individuals have been clearly identified in the California Earthquake Early Warning System Benefit Study (Johnson et al., 2016), where the potential relationships between EEW, OEF and RRE interventions to support improved community resilience were explored. In particular, the study focused on public safety/preservation of life as well as organisational preparedness to respond to, and recover from, an earthquake event. This deliverable explores these relationships in more detail, complementing the findings from the Californian study with a wider review of the socio-economic-political benefits of EEW, OEF and RRE systems reported in academic literature. The deliverable also reviews the overarching theory of community resilience to earthquake events to identify the key relationships between EEW, OEF and RRE systems and community resilience to earthquake events that will inform the design of the FWCR platform. The review also includes references to Japanese experience that either complements or contradicts the American experience. The theoretical relationship between OEF, EEW and RRE systems expressed as a chronological sequence is shown in Figure 2.1. In operationalising Figure 2.1 consideration needs to be given to both the technical and operational requirements of the different systems from the perspective of different end-user stakeholder groups (i.e. individual citizens, emergency responders, business organisations, and critical infrastructure operators) and of those national and regional organisations and authorities responsible for managing the dissemination of information about earthquake events. Therefore this deliverable explores the operational requirements OEF, EEW and RRE systems as they affect each end-user stakeholder group's contribution to improved community resilience to earthquake events across Europe.

Figure 2.1: Illustration of the chronological sequence of OEF, EEW and RRE
(source: extracted from TURNkey project proposal)

3 SOCIO-ECONOMIC-POLITICAL REVIEW OF EXISTING EARTHQUAKE EARLY WARNING (EEW) SYSTEMS

A global review of EEW systems was presented by Allen et al. (2009) as part of a special issue of Seismological Research Letters, and although the majority of the paper focused on the scientific and technological challenges of detecting and communicating earthquake early warnings, the paper also

considered the social lessons that could be learned from the different regional systems. Allen et al. provided a classification of EEW systems according to the number and position of sensors and scale of prediction and use and presented details of how the alert systems used in Mexico, Japan, Taiwan, Turkey and Romania provided information to end-users. Although each of the systems differed in terms of age, scope and intended reach, the systems all had common elements and faced similar social issues. All of the systems reviewed used a range of communication channels to provide different levels of warning to both the general public and specialist end-user groups. The communication channels typically comprised public radio and television broadcast media, as well as dedicated radio and cellular systems, and email.

Whilst the primary use of EEW amongst members of the general public across all the systems reviewed was to support their safety (Drop, Cover, Hold-on), the use amongst specialist end-user groups was more varied. Specialist end-user groups who typically receive EEW alerts include schools and universities, public building owners/managers, commercial enterprises, emergency and safety agencies, government agencies, critical infrastructure providers (particularly mass transit organisations, critical distribution nodes, health sector infrastructure, shopping malls and power generation facilities) and civil protection organisations. Whilst the specific use made of EEW alerts amongst the different type of end-user organisations depends on their specific circumstances, there is evidence that many business/critical infrastructure organisations have effectively integrated the alerts into their disaster management and business continuity planning. Specific examples of such integration include autonomous control of critical systems and processes (e.g. power shut-off and access control to transportation systems, shutdown of hazardous chemical processes, triggering 'safe-modes' for sensitive equipment and vertical transit systems etc.) and workplace safety alerts. Indeed, Allen et al. drew attention to the use made by private third-party providers of the JMA (Japan) to provide more focused alerts by integrating the general EEW alerts with data generated by local private seismometers to provide more detailed site-specific alerts that some critical infrastructure and large business organisations had used to calculate organisation specific risks for their operations. In the case of Tokyo Gas, for example, whilst the decision to close the major gas pipeline is 'human controlled' to minimize false-positive alerts, the gas meters installed for each individual user have an 'automatic' shut off system to reduce fire risk (Yamazaki, 2003).

Allen et al.'s (ibid) review also highlighted some common misconceptions and problems associated with the operation of EEW systems. These included unreasonable expectations amongst members of the general public of the warning time that could be given before shaking was experienced, insufficient operational funding for both the system and the education/outreach activities required to promote the system, the difficulty in attracting a large enough group of end-users (including members of the public) to the system, and problems of issuing false-positive and false-negative alerts (although in the author's opinion these could be avoided by setting different threshold levels for different end-user groups). However, one often cited concern, the potential panic that issuing an earthquake alert could cause amongst the general public, was not supported by the evidence reviewed by Allen et al. Indeed, the lack of panic, and the positive impact that providing time for the general public to mentally prepare for a shaking event, has been recognised in more recent studies as a positive aspect of EEW systems (Becker, 2019).

The public desire for EEW alerts can also be seen in Japan where earthquake risk is communicated through television and a sound alarm for an earthquake above a given threshold on the JMA scale. Moreover, the issuing of earthquake alerts has become a business opportunity for companies to analyse the data provided by the national service, JMA, and produce push notifications on smartphones through a pay-to-use apps, like “Yurekuru Call” produced by RCSolutions¹. The presence of a market for such apps or similar priced alert systems, in addition to the national alert issued by the public authorities, indicates the community’s wish to be prepared for earthquake events.

Finally, Allen et al. (ibid) identified a clear challenge to those earthquake-prone regions of the world that were considering the development of an EEW system: that of the need to engage in a detailed discourse with non-technical users/promoters about the benefits of such systems beyond the seismology community. To address this issue in Japan the JMA defined and adopted the JMA scale, which links earthquake intensity to risk perception (Figure 3.1).

¹ <https://www.rcsc.co.jp/> [website accessed on 29/08/2019]

Figure 3.1: The JMA scale
(source: DOI, 2011)

A more specific review of the perceived socio-economic-political benefits of EEW systems was undertaken by PEER - Pacific earthquake engineering research Centre for the California Governor's Office of Emergency Services and the California Seismic Safety Commission (Johnson et al., 2016). The PEER report examined the perceived benefits of a state-wide EEW to public and employee safety and business and community resilience through the protection of critical operations and assets before, during and after an earthquake event. Through 18 semi-structured interviews with 24 organisations representing infrastructure providers and the wider business community the report identified 14 potential application areas where EEW systems could potentially add value to either the Californian economy or the well-being of its citizens. The report further sought to identify those applications by their 'readiness for development' and identified the potential barriers to implementation.

The PEER study identified two types of societal benefit expected of an EEW system: the first related to individual members of society accessing the system, and the second related to the benefits that could accrue from different organisational sectors accessing the system.

There was unanimous agreement amongst respondents that the perceived benefit of individuals using an EEW system to take precautionary actions (e.g. drop, cover, and hold on) before strong ground shaking began would provide very high benefit to society. Many respondents also identified the educational benefit, and in particular raising the general level of awareness and preparedness of citizens for an earthquake event if an EEW system was operational. The educational benefits were also identified by Yamazaki (2003) where he identified the need for planning and investments to achieve the goal of building back better. Finally, many respondents also suggested that a range of socio-psychological benefits could be gained by giving society advance warning of ground shaking, including reducing anxiety when ground shaking began.

There was strong agreement amongst respondents that societal benefits could also result from different sectors of California's economy and infrastructure making use of a state-wide EEW. In particular, organisations could enhance employee safety and reduce the organisational time needed to address safety issues by directly informing employees to take preventative actions. There was also broad agreement that integrating the data emanating from an EEW system into disaster management and business continuity planning could reduce post event downtime and result in more rapid business and service recovery.

This said, the PEER study noted that for the above benefits to be realised would require clear challenges to be addressed and pathways for implementation identified. These included:

- A reliable EEW system that can provide large-scale broadcast notifications to people who are properly educated and trained in how to respond to the warnings from both a personal and business perspective;
- A detailed study of situationally-specific human and business activities that identify how EEW warnings are tailored to suit each activity. The situationally-specific activities need to consider different socio-demographic, organisational, temporal and functional situations, including the development of response protocols integrated into system/service design solutions;
- A reliable EEW that end-users can trust as accurate and helpful. In this context reliability is not viewed as a statistical concept but as a sociological construct;

- A recognition that achieving societal benefits from an EEW system requires an understanding of the complex interactions between the various systems and stakeholders that rely on each other for their performance during, and immediately after, an earthquake event; and
- A recognition of the importance that political, financial, equity and governance issues play in promoting and supporting an EEW system, including supporting those who take actions in response to a warning that might prove to be a false warning.

In order to explore the potential uses and benefits of an EEW system in more detail the PEER study asked respondents to identify the potential benefits and challenges that they would face when integrating an EEW system across 14 potential application areas. The potential application areas include (summarised from Table 3 of the PEER report and supplemented where appropriate with author notes):

1. **Notification for occupational safety:** alerts could be issued to individual employees to take situation-specific safety actions in preparation for ground shaking. Such actions could include machinery/equipment operations, evacuation from hazardous spaces where the impact of ground shaking could result in a high-risk to life. The latter would be particularly important to warn employees undertaking post-event inspections of imminent after-shocks. It was generally accepted that specific safety advice would need to be developed (*author's note: probably as part of disaster management planning*).
2. **Notification for public safety:** alerts and appropriate guidance could be given to members of the public on safety actions whilst on an organisations premises. Location-specific safety advice would need to be developed.
3. **Broadcast notification for general public safety:** it was generally accepted that all members of the general public should have access to EEW alerts through a variety of communication channels. Again situation/location-specific guidance would need to be developed that took account of individual citizens' personal circumstances (e.g. disabilities etc.).
4. **Triggering of emergency response plans:** organisations need to view an EEW alert as an input into their emergency response plans and ensure that these plans are triggered in an appropriate manner. This could include automated call systems to warn key personnel of imminent ground shaking or place organisational rapid response teams on alert.
5. **Large-scale utility control:** organisations would need to integrate EEW alerts into their disaster management control protocols and develop application-specific responses that could place equipment in a 'safe' mode and/or isolate parts of a utility system to reduce overall damage to the system (e.g. valves to shut off flow or switches to deactivate equipment). *Author's note: utility organisations would need to re-evaluate the level of redundancy within each system when designing disaster management control protocols.*
6. **On-site utility control:** as 5) above but including building specific disaster management control protocols and local redundancy systems (e.g. backup generators etc.).
7. **High-speed mass vehicle control:** control the deceleration (or in a small number of circumstances increase the acceleration) of high-speed vehicles to avoid hazardous conditions, particularly potential derailment or tunnel collapse. Depending upon system-specific conditions such control could be exercised through a control centre or in-vehicle.
8. **Low-speed mass vehicle control:** as 7) above but including on-site transport systems.

9. **Independent vehicle control:** alerts of imminent ground shaking would be sent to both human and robotic drivers of vehicles to place the vehicle in a 'safe' mode.
10. **Industrial equipment, asset and process control:** organisations would need to integrate EEW alerts into disaster management protocols to protect equipment and processes that would be highly susceptible to ground shaking. This would involve developing protocols to return the equipment to a 'safe' mode (*author's note: such protocols would have to consider the consequences of a 'safe' mode state on downstream/upstream operations*).
11. **Industrial chemical control:** organisations would have to develop disaster management protocols for controlling the flow of hazardous liquids, gases and other chemicals in industrial and manufacturing processes to reduce equipment damage and impact on the wider community (e.g. alarms for leak detection).
12. **Commercial equipment asset, and process control:** as 10) above organisations would have to develop disaster management protocols that would extend to off-site systems (e.g. remote IT services).
13. **Large-scale access control:** control of access and egress onto and off transportation networks.
14. **On-site access control:** organisations would need to develop disaster management protocols for access to and from (e.g. opening external doors to fire stations etc.) and around facilities or sites (e.g. health sector buildings etc.) (*author's note: for many organisations the above would be context-specific with the need to balance public/employee access to and from a facility with a security risk to the facility*).

Whilst respondents emphasised that although these application areas might be considered by their organisation, there were a number of barriers/issues which would need to be addressed if they were to be commercially developed. These barriers/issues included the need to:

1. Articulate EEW system performance metrics (objectives, resilience, redundancy and scalability) to provide organisations with the confidence to invest in the development of organisational specific applications.
2. Develop a governance structure for the management and operation of the EEW system that included representation from key stakeholders including scientists/engineers, emergency management responders, telecommunication industries, information technology industries, utility providers and experts in occupational behaviour, public health, psychology and community engagement.
3. Address the issue of liability and immunity should organisations take action if a false-positive or false-negative alert is issued that results in an adverse impact on third party organisations.
4. Equitable access is given to a EEW system that is effectively free to all. There was not strong support amongst respondents for a subscriber model.
5. Guarantee long-term funding for the EEW system to provide organisations with the confidence to invest in developing their organisation-specific applications.
6. Have a realistic timeframe plan to develop, implement and train the public on the use of the EEW system.
7. Ensure appropriate time was available to develop situationally-specific guidance that considers a range of socio-demographic, organisation, temple and functional situations.

However, it is important that this guidance is developed in advance of EEW system so that it can provide input into the design and budgeting of the system.

8. Ensure adequate training is provided, and in particular appropriate risk communication and public awareness campaigns are developed.

Many of the potential applications identified by the PEER report are already applied in Japan: High-speed mass vehicle control; Low-speed mass vehicle control; Independent vehicle control; Notification for public safety; Large-scale utility control and Industrial equipment, asset and process control (such as the Tokyo gas distribution network); Notification for occupational safety; and Notification for public safety (Yamazaki (2003); DOI (2011)).

In exploring the potential applications that an EEW could provide Californian organisations and citizens the PEER respondents mapped the 14 potential application areas against 6 organisational benefit categories: public safety; employee safety; property and asset protection; equipment and operations protection; business reputation and continuity; and business income and loss protection (Figure 3.2).

It is probably not unsurprising to those who work closely with organisational risk assessment and disaster management planning that the mapping relates very closely to most organisation's strategic objectives and business continuity and resilience plans. There was unanimous agreement amongst all respondents that overall life safety benefits to employees and the general public was ranked very high. Respondents all agreed that even a few seconds warning could help people take precautionary action before the onset of ground shaking. The perceived benefits of such actions included a reduction in the number of injuries and organisational time needed to address life-safety issues and complete life-safety assessments. The time saved would allow organisations to respond quicker, and implement targeted responses sooner, to reduce organisational downtime and disruption and reduce economic interruptions, all of which would benefit societal resilience as a whole. Although not unanimous, many respondents also identified psychological benefits as key to reducing anxiety when ground shaking began.

In an attempt to identify the level of priority that respondents placed on each potential application PEER developed a benefits matrix (Figure 3.2) derived from a consensus view across all sectors of the primary (P) and secondary (S) benefits of each potential application to elements of business continuity and resilience planning.

	Public Safety	Employee safety	Property and asset protection	Equipment/ operations protection	Business resumption/ continuity	Business income/loss protection
Occupational safety	S	P	S	S	S	S
Public Safety in a facility	P	P	S	S	S	S
General public safety	P	S	S	S	S	S
Activation of emergency response plans	S	P	P	P	S	S
Large-scale utility control	S	S	P	P	S	S

On-site facility control	S	S	P	P	S	S
High-speed mass vehicle control	P	P	P	P	S	S
Low-speed mass vehicle control	P	P	P	P	S	S
Independent vehicle control	P	P	P	S	S	S
Industrial equipment, asset and process control	S	P	P	P	P	P
Industrial chemical control	S	P	P	P	P	P
Commercial equipment, asset and process control	S	P	P	P	P	P
Large-scale access control	P	P	S	S	S	S
On-site facility access control	P	P	S	S	S	S

Figure 3.2: Primary and secondary benefits associated with potential application areas and impact on potential organisational benefits

(source: Table 4 PEER report number 2016/06)

It is clear that all of the potential application areas had some organisational benefits associated with them. However, whilst there would appear to be a correlation between those that were considered a priority related to specific use types (e.g. occupational safety being primarily related to employee safety, industrial equipment, asset and process control being primarily related to organisations resilience planning etc.), there did appear to be a causal and time sequential association with life safety and protection of property, asset, equipment and operations being the primary and crucial benefits that organisations believe they must achieve first to allow them to realise benefits of business resumption, continuity and income loss protection.

The relationship between potential applications and business resilience and continuity planning will be explored in more detail with end-user stakeholders in each of the 6 Testbeds.

Finally, the PEER study examined a range of key operational issues that would need to be considered when specifying an EEW system and designing end-user specific applications as part of business continuity and resilience planning (either from the private or public sector perspectives).

The first operational issue explored concerned human controlled versus automated applications in response to an EEW alert. Respondents were asked to identify potential applications that involved human controlled decisions and actions, and those that could be automated (assuming to technology existed). Whilst it was difficult to identify clear trends from the responses the report did identify the apparent preference for human controlled approaches rather than automated approaches from both a feasibility and willingness perspectives. The one area where automated control was considered both feasible and the organisations were willing to use automated control was in high-speed mass vehicle control (and in Japan the automatic control of valves of aqueducts). Whilst it was not clear as to why organisations didn't consider automation as the main response to the EEW warnings it could be related to a lack of feasible technology to automate responses, or to concern within organisations of the liability they could incur if an automated system resulted in a wrong action being taken. There appeared to be a view that the number of wrong actions would be reduced if the final decision remained within human

control. Indeed the PEER report (ibid) states that "... Maintaining the status quo is better than making a wrong decision or a decision that impacts the natural flow of events".

The second operational issue concerned sensitivities and organisational considerations that would affect the potential ability and willingness of organisations to use an EEW system. Respondents expressed the sensitivities and organisational considerations at both the EEW system and organisational operational levels. Key sensitivities at the system level included: reliability and trust (and understanding uncertainties), notifiable thresholds and in particular the need for different thresholds for different types of user, length of time for an advanced warning with the potential benefits to organisations and value of investing increasing as warning times increase (although it was noted that the time to take action was highly variable between companies, industries and systems). With regards to organisational considerations respondents identified: the lead time taken to develop appropriate technology and protocols to integrate the EEW alerts into organisational operating procedures, IT security, firewall and software issues that would have to be considered before internal systems could be open to receive automated alerts, personnel and training commitments, organisational leadership and interdepartmental coordination, the costs associated with developing and deploying systems and training employees, and legal and regulatory issues that could require changes in licences to operate.

The final operational issue concerned interdependencies between the different sectoral stakeholders and the potential application areas for an EEW system. While sectoral interdependency is a complicated issue the PEER report associated 1 of 3 interdependency levels between 14 sectoral stakeholders and the 14 potential application areas. Tier 1 interdependencies were defined as those that were critical to a sector's ability to access and use an EEW system. The three most critical tier 1 interdependencies relate to an organisations need to access electricity, telecommunications, and information technology. Tier 2 interdependencies were defined as those dependencies that each sector would rely on for real-time operations but that may be disrupted by an earthquake event, but that could be mitigated by the use of an EEW system. Tier 2 interdependencies included transportation systems, gas and water utilities systems public safety, and financial sectors. Tier 3 interdependencies relate primarily to those systems needed to restore function following an earthquake event. Tier 3 interdependencies include mass transit, health sector, education sector, insurance, business and commercial and industrial sectors. In addition to the above several respondents identified government agencies and community-based/non-profit agencies as important interdependencies. Finally, respondents also examined the interdependencies that affected supply chain logistics (upstream and downstream), developing an integrated view of the interrelationships between an EEW system, critical lifelines, social-serving sectors and economic-serving sectors (Figure 3.3).

Figure 3.3: Integrated view of Telecommunications, Electricity Utility, and Information Technology Sectors in the Functionality of an EEW system and its Key Sectors and Society as a Whole (source: PEER, 2016)

The TURNkey project will examine all of the above with end-users in the 6 testbeds.

Another aspect examined by the PEER study was the Relationship between EEW and earthquake preparedness and response planning. The PEER study adopted the proposition that the benefits that could accrue from an EEW system were incrementally based on the system's capacity to improve outcomes relative to what would have occurred under existing emergency response plans and preparedness activities. To test this proposition respondents were asked to describe their baseline state and discuss how the application of an EEW system would improve on the baseline. Although the responses given are specific to the Californian context, the general views should inform the TURNkey project. There were two main areas where organisation's believed EEW systems could have key

benefits. Although most respondents' organisations had invested in preparing for an earthquake event (had plans in place for evaluating the earthquake threat and coordinating their emergency response), it was believed that integrating an effective EEW into these plans would force a fundamental review that could address issues of organisational culture and 'silos' which would improve the coordination between those responsible for emergency management, which would in turn raise the response above the current baseline level. Currently most response actions to an earthquake event are reactive and not proactive. Individuals seek to secure their own safety, and then the safety of others; control centres seek to monitor and issue control driven by a series of playbooks or scenarios; and emergency responders react to calls from citizens or businesses. In such reactive systems the leadership structure, common understanding of roles and protocols, and preparations for response among all employees are critical, more importantly they take time to initiate responses. Proactive systems driven by EEW could change this approach and reduce the time taken for response actions to be initiated. The report did gather some evidence of such proactive thinking amongst that small group of users who were using the ShakeAlert and ShakeCast systems.

Finally, the PEER report recognised the limitations of the study and made specific suggestions for further research to quantify the benefits of EEW systems. In particular the PEER report identified the need for:

1. The development of a robust set of scenarios for each application area that explicitly addressed the user specific cases and prioritised the most promising applications. It was suggested that user centred design be used as the basis for identifying a set of high-quality use-cases that provide detailed descriptions of the specific scenarios in each application area. In developing the use-cases it is important to adopt a multidisciplinary approach that reflects all of the stakeholders involved in preparing for, and responding to, an earthquake event.
2. Detailed testing of delivery models and warning responses to maximise the potential life safety benefits of EEW systems. It is important that these investigations cover a range of sociodemographic, organisation, temporal and functional situations.
3. The collection of quantitative evidence about the likelihood of different application scenarios and their benefits. In essence, each use-case scenario should be detailed enough to allow the effects of different operational decisions to be evaluated. This would inevitably include the development of cost-benefit analyses at both an organisational and community level.
4. A wider systematic review of the attitudes towards EEW systems across a wide range of sectors to support the cost-benefit analysis followed by a critical analysis of the issues that will ultimately be needed to support the business case for EEW system development.

Whilst the above summary provides an overview of the potential application areas, issues, and potential benefits associated with the development of an EEW: the authors strongly recommend that all members of the TURNkey project read the full PEER report to identify specifically how the TURNkey project relates these issues to their particular work packages and tasks.

On 17 October 2019 California announced the launch of a state-wide earthquake early warning system. The system, which is based around providing California residents with earthquake alerts, seeks to

minimise the damage caused by earthquakes and save lives by providing Californian residents with a few seconds to prepare for a shaking event. The earthquake alerts will be delivered by a smart phone app (MyShake developed by the University of California) or through automated wireless public safety alerts that will allow people and organisations to take actions (e.g. slow down public transport, open fire house doors, stop elevators, discontinue surgeries etc.) in preparation for a shaking event². The TURNkey project will continue to monitor the developments and implementation of the Californian system and integrate any lessons learnt into the TURNkey use-cases.

Whilst the PEER review summarised the latest thinking on the potential application and benefits that could accrue from an EEW system, many other authors have examined specific socio-economic-political benefits or application issues associated with other EEW systems, particularly those that have been deployed in Japan, Taiwan and Mexico. A summary of the benefits/issues that have been identified is given in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Review of perceived benefits/application issues for EEW systems

Source	Perceived benefits/application issues
Auclair et al. (2014)	There is a clear need to understand the situational context and end-user needs of any EEW system when assessing their feasibility. This understanding needs to include both system requirements/expectations and attitudes towards risk. This understanding also needs to address the range of end-user stakeholders who will potential use the system.
Becker J. S. (2019)	Presented preliminary results from an investigation into the possibility of developing an EEW for New Zealand. The presentation identified the need to consider the requirements of different end-user groups when identifying trigger thresholds and alert delivery channels as well as developing specific applications for the different end-user groups. The presentation identified a general level of support amongst the New Zealand public for an EEW system that supported improved public health and safety and mental preparedness. This said there were public reservations about stopping functions/systems that could be hard to restart once ground shaking ceased. The public were more likely to consider using EEW actions for “easy to turn on again” systems. Such opportunities need to be identified on a sector by sector basis. The presentation identified the potential for alert fatigue if too many false-positive warnings were issued which would again suggest the need to engage the end-user groups in defining risk tolerances and triggering thresholds.
Becker et al. (2019)	Although the focus of this paper is on after-shock information needs some of the findings would be applicable for those developing EEW (and OEF) systems; including the findings on the factors that influenced public perception of the relevance and understanding of the information provided. The paper concluded that a range of factors including whether people had prior knowledge or experience of after-shocks, whether the information was personalised or contextualised, individual emotions and feelings, credibility

² <https://eos.org/articles/california-launches-nations-first-earthquake-early-warning-system>

	and trust in the system, and external influences all affected the perception of the system's performance. Further, the paper concluded that the information needs of agencies and the public evolved throughout the earthquake sequence depending upon the impacts experienced by people and the roles the people were performing. The content and format of the information therefore needs to be contextualised to reflect the very specific needs of the different end-user groups and reflect their position in the prepare-respond-recover disaster process.
Becker et al. (2015)	Although the focus of the paper is on after-shock information needs of those organisations directly involved in responding to and supporting recovery from after-shocks during the Canterbury earthquake sequence the findings are applicable to those developing EEW (and OEF) systems. In particular the paper identified the information needed by: search and rescue, emergency managers, structural/geotechnical engineers, civil infrastructure providers, business organisations, construction managers, insurers, policymakers and recovery leaders at different phases of the earthquake sequence (response phase, readiness phase, recovery/reduction phase). In identifying the information needs the paper highlighted the complex environment that exists during an earthquake sequence and the impact that different timeframes have on the ability to deliver effective warnings that the end-user groups can act on.
Becker et al. (2012)	Although not directly related to the role of EEW the paper used symbolic interactionism to explore how people interpret earthquake information and use this to inform their preparedness measures. A model outlining the preparedness process was presented that draws together leadership, participation, trust, responsibility, a sense of community and social norms/influences as precursors to identifying the requirements that individuals have to prepare for an earthquake event. The model provides a number of touch points in the preparedness process that the TURNkey EEW (and OEF) systems need to engage with, either to provide information, or to understand the context within which the information is interpreted and acted. This will be picked up in more detail in TURNkey WP5.
Bose et al. (2013)	Recognises the need to provide education and training in how different end-user groups could respond to ground shaking alerts. This needs to include both automated response procedures and individual actions.
Cauzzi et al. (2016)	Mitigation actions of an EEW could involve shutdown of primary and secondary systems, early activation of emergency plans, automatic opening of on-site fire station doors. A key issue with automated systems is to ensure consistency with the regulatory framework under which critical infrastructure providers operate. This potentially involves the identification of critical (time-dependent) decision factors that need to be integrated into disaster management planning.
Cimellaro G. P. (2016)	Although this book is not directly related to the role of EEW systems it does provide a very broad overview of the factors and issues that affect urban resilience on the perspective of emergency response and recovery.

DOI. K. (2011)	Identifies the need to focus EEW alerts to the needs of different end-user stakeholder groups (advance users and the general public). Whilst advanced users were able to understand and respond to system alerts appropriately the general public find it difficult to understand the sudden EEW notification. There is a clear need for widespread public education program to support the introduction of an EEW system.
Douglas, J. and Woo, G. (2012)	Identifies the need to engage end-users in identifying and developing response actions to EEW alerts that consider end-user tolerance to false-positive alarms when setting trigger levels. Such tolerances need to consider community values as well as scientific data. For the general public it was suggested that a collective approach was adopted when members of the general public have an input into the decision process but that key civil protection agencies alone make the final decision. For owners/operators of specific assets the final decision would belong to the assets owner/manager but that this decision would be informed by appropriate scientific expert advice.
Dunn et al. (2016)	From a survey of residents report identified that past experience, risk perception of earthquake events and familiarity with EEW systems as key factors in understanding individual citizens propensity to take preparations for an earthquake event.
Goltz, J. D. (2014)	The presentation explored human behaviour in response to earthquake early warnings and identified the critical need for training as a precursor to survival avoidance of injury in a major earthquake. The presentation also identified the need for collaboration between physical scientists, engineers, social scientists and emergency managers to maximise the potential of EEW systems to identify and manage situations in which hazards can be mitigated in a time frame of a few seconds to a few tens of seconds and to develop life safety measures to help people protect themselves in different situations. Both of these need to be developed with an understanding of the demographic and social characteristics of the different target audiences receiving EEW alerts.
Hamilton et al. (2011)	Developed a roadmap to describe the actions and activities needed to reduce the risks associated with earthquake events. The roadmap mapped 18 tasks against 14 strategic objectives including the role of EEW and OEF systems. At a strategic level EEW was seen to primarily influence improved understanding of processes and impacts and improved community resilience. EEW systems were not seen as a cost effective way to reduce these impacts. On the contrary OEF systems were seen as a cost effective way to reduce impacts as well as improving community resilience. The key benefits of EEW systems were identified as improving public safety, informing and triggering safe operating practices for critical infrastructure and business and reducing building damage. The key benefits of OEF systems were identified as providing reliable information to allow citizens and organisations prepare and plan for an earthquake event.

Minson et al. (2017)	There is a need to understand end-user tolerance levels, particularly tolerance for false-positive ground motion alerts, if the full potential of EEW systems are to be realised.
Nakamura et al. (2011)	Integrating EEW into real-time disaster management (before during and after ground shaking) requires reliable information on areas that will and will not be damaged and an estimate of the extent of the area where serious damage (<i>author's note: as defined by the end-user</i>) can be expected. This in turn needs to be integrated into organisational and emergency responder disaster management plans. The reliability of generic EEW systems can be enhanced with the integration of on-site detection/alarm systems.
Nakayachi, et al. (2019)	Through two web-based panel studies recipients of EEW alerts were asked a range of questions to gauge their experience of, and response to the alerts. Whilst respondents demonstrated a range of reactions from, do nothing to help others, most respondents in both studies did nothing/took no actions. When asked what they would do next time most responded that they would mentally prepare themselves for a shaking event. When respondents were asked why they took the action they took (including doing nothing) the majority replied that they expected only a small intensity earthquake and as such thought it was unnecessary to take further action, or thought they were safe where they were. In conclusion the study suggested the need for further research to understand people's reactions/actions when they receive an EEW alert and to revisit the 'action' messaging. The study also suggested a wider public education/training program to reduce optimism bias and negative outcome expectancy and enhance positive outcome expectancy.
Pagano, L. and Sica, S. (2013)	EEW could provide guidance on post-seismic safety assessments of earth dams (cascading scenarios) including, early assessment of physical integrity and triggering of system specific inspections. Such systems would need to integrate EEW alert levels with failure modes analysis of critical systems.
Rainieri et al. (2010)	Identifies the opportunity to integrate EEW systems into the design and operation of structural health monitoring applications. These include context specific critical infrastructure and built asset disaster management plans that integrate on-site sensors with external EEW systems to facilitate immediate and post ground shaking responses, including control of human and physical resources and condition assessment of critical assets.
Satriano, et al. (2011)	Identifies the need for those developing EEW applications to understand the trade-off between time and accuracy when addressing the needs of different end-user groups (e.g. at the general population level or site-specific user level).
Strauss, J. A. And Allen, R. M. (2016)	Provides a detailed review of the potential mitigation activities by sector that could result from an EEW system. For hospitals these include: stopping surgery safely, temporarily disconnecting ventilator tubes, opening doors to provide egress routes, closing blinds/curtains to minimise glass debris, raising awareness of falling hazards, securing dangerous chemical sources, placing equipment into safe mode, changing clinical practices to stabilise patients quickly, implementing emergency plans. For schools these include:

	<p>closing curtains to prevent injury from broken glass, opening classrooms doors to ensure egress and raising awareness of falling hazards. For emergency responders these include: opening doors to ensure egress of personnel and equipment, activating emergency operations centres, providing situational awareness and triggering disaster management plans. For elevators these include: returning elevators the ground floor or activating emergency shutdown procedures before strong ground shaking occurs. For manufacturing these include: isolating hazardous chemicals and systems and activating automated controls to reduce secondary effects. For critical infrastructure and lifelines these include: immediate estimates of damage state and location, access of disaster management and business continuity plans. For transportation systems these include: situational awareness of potential ground shaking to enable systems to be switched to a 'safer' operating mode.</p>
Wenzel et al. (2001)	<p>Potential uses of an EEW system include automatic trigger measures (e.g. shutdown of computers, rerouting of electrical power, shutdown of vibration sensitive equipment, shutdown or activation of alternate management of transportation systems, shutdown of power and water distribution systems, alerting of hospitals and issuing of audio alarms to citizens).</p>
Yamasaki, E. (2011)	<p>In addition to identifying information needs of different user groups the report identified the strong role the culture plays in responding to earthquake alerts. The report pointed to the 'proactive culture' of Japanese Society along with a propensity for Japanese people to be very detailed-orientated, precise and cautious which combined with the proactive culture fosters a mindset of disaster preparedness.</p>

In addition to the specific benefits of EEW identified above, a number of authors (Gobbato et al., 2019; Strauss and Allen, 2016; Lieberman, 2015) have examined the costs associated with implementing EEW systems and developed approaches to evaluate the cost-benefit ratio of such systems.

Gobbato et al. (2019) used the RMS (Risk Management Solutions) catastrophe earthquake model applied over a 30 year time frame to estimate avoided losses in terms of mortality/morbidity, secondary impacts (e.g. fire) and commercial losses that would be experienced by a wide range of commercial stakeholders (e.g. hospitals and clinics, retirement homes, the hospitality industry, the entertainment industry, the construction industry, manufacturing industry, the aviation and automotive industry, and the agricultural sector). The costs were discounted and offset against future benefits to make the economic arguments to support the development of an EEW system across the West Coast of the USA.

Strauss and Allen (2016) used FEMA's cost-benefit methodology for hazard mitigation projects to show that the saving of three lives; the warning of two semiconductor plants; the slowing of one train; a 1% reduction in morbidity, and a 0.25% avoidance of gas-related fire damage could pay for one year operation of a USA West Coast EEW system.

Lieberman (2015) used a Costs Avoided model of reduced casualties as a consequence of an EEW system as the basis of their cost-benefit model. Lieberman (ibid) quantified the costs of casualties by

monetising the four casualty category levels used by FEMA (FEMA, 2009) and estimating the effectiveness of distance (as a proxy for warning lead time to ground shaking), uptake, and ability to take action for five USA West Coast earthquake scenarios. Lieberman (ibid) calculated both the implementation and operational costs, including the impact of false alarms, to show that over a 50 year period the net present value of developing and operating an EEW system would be in the order of \$20 million. Given that Lieberman did not consider any benefits other than the reduction in human mortality or morbidity it is likely that his cost-benefit estimate is considerably lower than that which would be realised in practice.

In addition to the specific application of cost-benefit analysis to EEW systems Jones et al. (2019) performed a fundamental review of alternative approaches to disaster risk reduction cost-benefit analysis as part of the LIQUEFACT project. Jones et al. extended the cost-benefit methodology developed for assessing the impact of wide area disaster events to include an options appraisal cost-benefit methodology as part of a resilience assessment and improvement framework that could be applied at the individual built asset level. This methodology will be extended in the TURNkey project to estimate the benefits of an EEW to a wide range of critical infrastructure and business organisations; most likely by developing a methodology to evaluate Willingness To Pay and/or Willingness To Accept metrics into an integrated cost-benefit model.

4 SOCIO-ECONOMIC-POLITICAL REVIEW OF OPERATIONAL EARTHQUAKE FORECASTING (OEF) SYSTEMS

Whilst there have been a number of socio-economic-political benefit studies of EEW systems, there are far fewer studies of the socio-economic-political benefits of OEF systems.

Operational earthquake forecasting systems are a collection of procedures for gathering and disseminating authoritative information about the time dependence of seismic hazards to help communities prepare for earthquake events (Jordan et al., 2011). The TURNkey project will utilise the FWCR platform to collate and manage all long-term earthquake-hazard related information, and through the multi-sensor-based earthquake information system, monitor short-term changes to this information (TURNkey Grant Agreement, 2019). Critical to this task is the need to develop criteria that validate any observed changes and governs the dissemination of subsequent warnings. With regard to the latter, it is important that any time-dependent hazard changes are transmitted in an understandable and useful format to end-users. As such, the focus of this section is to present the current 'state-of-the-art' of potential end-uses and end-user needs that will guide the development of the FWCR OEF system for improved community resilience to earthquake events.

Unlike EEW systems, the authors could find very little research into the socio-economic-political benefits of OEF systems from either the organisational or community resilience perspective. Those studies that have been undertaken have tended to focus on identifying the technical/modelling aspects required of OEF systems rather than their role in earthquake planning for improved organisational/community resilience. The remainder of this section summarises the key findings of those studies that have, either directly or indirectly, addressed socio-economic-political benefits of OEF systems.

Probably the most authoritative review of the potential applications and benefits of OEF system was reported by Field et. al. (2016) following a two-day workshop (held in March 2015 and supported by the U.S. Geological Survey John Wesley Powell Centre for Analysis and Synthesis, the Southern California Earthquake Centre, and the U.S. Geological Survey Science Application for Risk Reduction programme) that explored the potential uses of OEF systems. The workshop considered the potential of OEF systems to provide time-dependent earthquake probability forecasts ranging from a few hours to decades. The workshop also examined how such forecasts could help communities prepare for earthquakes by providing reliable information to help mitigate seismic risk. The workshop identified the potential for OEF systems to generate forecasts of event probabilities and ground motion hazards over timescales of 1 day to 50 years and to produce a range of loss metrics such as: expected number of collapsed buildings, displaced residents, injuries and fatalities. Such information can be used to inform emergency response disaster policy and future land planning including rebuilding decisions (as in Christchurch, New Zealand) and to inform building design codes. In developing and disseminating forecasts and metrics, specific attention needs to be given to the end-user needs of different stakeholder groups, and to the format used to disseminate information to these groups. This said, one critical aspect of dissemination is to ensure consistency of message between different stakeholder groups. This is particularly true if forecasts are disseminated to different stakeholder groups at different triggering thresholds. Mixed or ambiguous messages given to different groups can lead to confusion and potential problems around misinformation or uncoordinated response actions. In this context it is important to ensure that OEF systems are complete, transparent and 'policy neutral'. Finally the workshop identified the need to provide a level of information that is consistent with, and able to support, cost-benefit analysis of alternate potential mitigation interventions.

In addition to identifying the generic potential applications and benefits of OEF systems the workshop (ibid) also explored the specific attributes (in terms of OEF information, metrics and products) that would be needed by different end-user stakeholder groups. To this end the workshop identified the following key (desirable) information attributes of an OEF system:

- Spatial distributions specifying where earthquake events are most likely to occur;
- Magnitude probability distributions of the likelihood of earthquakes of different magnitudes in an area over a specified time period;
- Earthquake rupture forecasts for a given time period;
- Hazard estimates that give the probability of an earthquake event exceeding intensity measure thresholds and ground deformation probabilities;
- Earthquake sequence duration and examples of earthquake scenarios; and
- Cascading probabilities including landslides and liquefaction etc.

Based on the above the workshop (ibid) further identified a number of 'downstream' hazard risk assessments that could translate the key information into end-user metrics and products (models) to support improved earthquake preparations and planning. These include:

- Population and/or infrastructure exposure models that give an estimate of the likelihood of hazard thresholds been exceeded and predict damage levels and collapse probabilities of critical assets and infrastructures against a range of thresholds (*author's note: as community resilience relies heavily on the continued functionality of critical systems and services after an earthquake event it is important that these models report damage levels and collapse*

probabilities against functionality thresholds as well as serviceability and ultimate limit state thresholds);

- Critical assets and infrastructure downtime models to assess the likelihood and length of disruption to businesses, horizontal critical infrastructure, healthcare infrastructure, telecommunication and communication systems including inspection priority or concern levels identifying a list of assets that require specific attention. (*author's note: as modern businesses and critical infrastructure systems are all interdependent on each other for delivering their core services it is important that downtime assessments include the impact that upstream and downstream logistics supply chains have on the post-earthquake business continuity of critical infrastructure organisations);*
- Mortality and morbidity estimates to inform health care infrastructure planning and insurance losses, risks and liability. Loss data will also be required to inform cost-benefit models to evaluate the economic feasibility of potential mitigation interventions to reduce earthquake-related disaster risks.

It was noted (ibid) that in developing all of the above the effects of uncertainties (in metrics and models) would have to be fully understood by those developing the products and communication protocols would have to be developed to effectively communicate the effect of these uncertainties to non-technical end-users.

Finally, the workshop (ibid) also explored how the metrics and products could be packaged together to provide practical guidance to different end-user groups to support their improved resilience (as individual groups and collectively as communities) to earthquake events. These include:

- **Increased public preparedness:** through issuing detailed individual guidance on family emergency plans (checking food, water, medical supplies, mobile phones, fuel, and access to cash); household safety plans (securing household objects, vulnerability assessments, structural retrofits, insurance needs); providing information to allow individuals to assess relocation/rebuilding options after an earthquake event; and supporting communitywide education programs. Appropriate messaging (using a mix of quantitative and qualitative language) is essential if increased public preparedness is to be effective. To this end it is critical that warnings are timely and accompanied by specific information about what actions to take, and when, and that this information comes from a source that people trust. To this end it is important that warnings are transparent and include full disclosure; this improves confidence and reassurance to the public that earthquake events have been planned for.
- **Supporting advice given by official agencies:** OEF systems can provide information to assist emergency responders/managers and civic protection agencies plan their responses to a range of earthquake scenarios. However, to plan their responses effectively these organisations need to effectively integrate OEF system products and metrics into their disaster management plans. As different levels of emergency responders/management exist at different levels of government and in private organisations it is critical that OEF systems provide a range of information that can be tailored by each organisation to match their specific requirements and capabilities. Large organisations or critical infrastructure providers are likely to require regular, detailed information, whereas small organisations or individual businesses are likely to require more generic information to inform disaster management/business continuity plans and risk assessments as well as provide scenarios

against which to test disaster-response operating procedures and protocols. From a civic protection/regional planning perspective OEF systems could provide zoning information to inform the location of emergency shelters or the storage of emergency equipment away from high hazard areas. For search and rescue organisations OEF systems, if linked to structural health monitoring systems, could provide a rapid assessment of the structural integrity of buildings and the risks associated with entering or re-occupying a building after an earthquake event. In the case of this potential application, understanding the uncertainties in predictions would be critical to the confidence that emergency responders place in the advice and guidance.

- **Regional land use planning:** OEF systems can inform long-term land zoning, providing probability and risk information to the public, property developers, insurers and capital markets. Such information and models could be used to inform building code standards and support the management of large-scale financial risks.
- **Supply chain logistics:** OEF systems can provide planning information for businesses continuity and resilience models allowing businesses to assess their resilience (and that of their supply chain) to earthquake events (*author's note: understanding the resilience of supply chains is critical for many modern organisations, particularly in the retail sector, where just-in-time restocking systems have become the norm. Even if a retail outlet is not directly affected by an earthquake event its ability to function could be severely affected if goods and services cannot be shipped along its supply chain*).

Whilst Field et. al. (2016) provide a detailed overview of the potential benefits/applications and key considerations for developing of OEF systems, other authors have examined specific socio-economic-political benefits or application issues associated with OEF systems. A summary of the benefits/issues that have been identified are given in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1: Review of perceived benefits/application issues for OEF systems

Source	Perceived benefits/application issues
Becker J. S. (2019)	Identified the difficulty faced by stakeholders in understanding and interpreting OEF system information, and in applying it to personal and business decision-making. There is a need to develop templates and scenarios to help end-users interpret the outputs from OEF systems at a range of triggering thresholds that reflect the different needs of different users. Whilst such templates and scenarios could inform education programs to promote a greater understanding amongst the general public and business organisations of OEF systems, because of the infrequency of earthquake events these educational programs need to be repeated at regular intervals.
Becker et al. (2019)	Although this paper is primarily concerned with the interpretation of after-shock information some of the issues are relevant to OEF systems. In particular the degree to which prior knowledge or experience of an earthquake event; how understandable and relevant the forecast information is; whether the forecast information is personalised or contextualised; cultural context, credibility and trust, affect the interpretation of forecasts. For

	<p>example: emergency responders require information about where it will be safe to enter buildings or where they might need to place cordons or exclusion zones; structural/geotechnical engineers need information to develop a RAG system for buildings and critical infrastructure assets; critical infrastructure providers need information to identify resources needed to respond to the earthquake events and to determine the repair scope and timing of repair actions; communication companies need information for public awareness and public response; business representatives need information about damage profiles for business continuity plans; construction managers and insurers need information for timing of repairs and rebuild; and policymakers need information to develop appropriate building standards and regional zoning maps.</p>
Cauzzi et al. (2016)	<p>Identified that mitigation guidance is provided by OEF systems has to be consistent with the regulatory framework for the management of emergency situations pertinent to the sector.</p>
Douglas et al. (2012)	<p>Identified the role the participatory decision-making in responding to OEF systems warnings and guidance, and in particular emphasised the role that communities should play in the development of guidance and the interpretation of priorities for action. OEF system designers need to be aware of the different risk thresholds (or personal attitude to risk) that inform citizens/organisations response to warnings and triggering of mitigation plans. Also, OEF system designers must be aware of the potential impact that system warnings and guidance may have on organisations that may not be directly affected by an earthquake event but who nevertheless may lose business negative publicity.</p>
Jordan et al. (2011)	<p>Identified the need for OEF systems to be transparent, consistent and objective and to properly convey the uncertainties associated with forecasts, which need to effectively support decision-making by different end-user stakeholder groups. To this end, protocols are required to translate the probabilities from OEF systems into specific guidance to support mitigation actions and preparedness, including cost-benefit analyses. Currently most OEF assessments are transmitted to decision-makers who act as gatekeepers between the scientists and end-users who issue alerts and guidance, but the use of web-based technology could make OEF available directly to the public on a continuous basis. As such OEF systems could provide a psychological benefit to the public by filling information vacuums and combating informal predictions and misinformation.</p>

The one issue not yet explored in this section is that of the integration of OEF systems into cost-benefit models for reduced earthquake disaster risk. Although Field et al. (2016) and Cauzzi et al. (2016) identified the need for OEF systems to provide information to support cost-benefit models, it was Woo and Marzocchi. (2016) who explored the relationships in detail, developing a cost-benefit modelling methodology to demonstrate how human decisions could be supported by OEF systems to justify

investment in low-cost mitigation interventions (e.g. personal vigilance, preparedness, earthquake drills and training, discretionary travel, short-term relocation, and low-cost building interventions like securing items etc.) even when the probability of an earthquake event was very low. This in turn they argued could address the legacy of non-earthquake building code compliant buildings (based primarily on age) by supporting the 'nudge' approach to devolved decision-making which could provide significant risk reduction (5% - 10%) for occupants of seismically vulnerable buildings and even reduce mortality rates by a few percent ahead of longer term retrofitting. Finally, Woo and Marzocchi also suggested that exposing individuals to the cost-benefit modelling approach forced them to examine their attitudes to risk, and in some cases could persuade them to change their risk thresholds.

Finally, whilst it is generally accepted amongst the papers reviewed that's OEF systems have significant potential value, particularly with respect to aiding individual and organisational pre-earthquake preparations, Field et al. (2016) drew particular attention for the need for such systems to be carefully designed and tested before an earthquake event. Field et al. further reminded those developing OEF systems that their role is primarily to inform, and not prescribe responses, to changing seismic hazards and risk. As such Field et al. stressed the importance of carefully integrating OEF information into applications that reflects different end-user stakeholders groups needs when preparing for, and responding to, earthquake disaster events. Above all Field et al. emphasised that OEF systems must not act as a point of confusion for members of the public, and as such emphasised the importance of integrating OEF systems with the mitigation advice given by proper authorities and administered by appropriate organisations.

5 SOCIO-ECONOMIC-POLITICAL REVIEW OF RAPID RESPONSE TO EARTHQUAKES (RRE) SYSTEMS

Whilst there have been a number of socio-economic-political benefit studies of EEW and OEF systems the authors have found far fewer studies that have specifically examined socio-economic-political benefits of RRE systems. Indeed, where reference has been made to RRE systems these have mainly addressed the roles that EEW and OEF can play in supporting emergency responders, either as individual agencies or as part of a coordinated civic/emergency sector response, to earthquake events (Paton et al., 2017). Paton et al. examined the psychological issues that emergency responders faced when dealing with sudden critical incidents. Paton et al. drew attention to the need for emergency service organisation to have processes and systems in place to enhance and support the personal resilience of the emergency responders who have to deal with the aftermath of a disaster event. Such support includes: psychological awareness and mental preparedness (many disaster events occur with very little warning), training in response to threatening conditions and unforeseen events, the need to make quick decisions that are outside their normal sphere of responsibility, and post-event support systems to deal with post-traumatic stress and reintegrate emergency responders back into their normal roles and routines. With regard to the latter, Paton et al. identified a range of risk factors (media reporting and socio-legal processes that might criticise organisational and individual responder performance during an event, mental health management, performance reviews, catching up on a backlog of work, and readjusting to their normal working routine) that whilst they do not determine the outcome of critical incidents directly, nevertheless impact on personal and team and organisational dynamics. Consequently Paton et al. identified the need to understand how such dynamics influenced the functional response of emergency responders to the next critical event.

In exploring these characteristics further Paton et al. (ibid) identified the role that empowerment can play in providing an understanding and context of resilience and support those frontline officers to 'make sense of' the situation is that they find themselves in. Paton et al. also identified the role of organisational culture, including team cohesion and support, trust, along with family and personal factors that can help emergency responders manage the high levels of stress that they experience during the course of a disaster event. Finally Paton et al. integrated a range of personal, team, organisational and inter-organisational resources into a critical incident stress resilience model (Figure 5.1) that could provide the basis of training programmes and organisational needs analyses to support effective emergency responder capabilities (see chapter 17 for more details on how the model can directly influence training needs).

Figure 5.1: Critical Incidents Stress Model
(source: Paton & Johnston, 2016)

Although Paton et al. (ibid) did not directly link the resources identified in Figure 5.1 to the effectiveness of RRE actions the authors would argue that the existence of processes and systems that recognise, and can mobilise, resources should result in a more effective rapid response to earthquake events. As such the authors would further argue that many of the perceived socio-economic-political benefits that could be attributed to RRE systems are the same as those attributed to critical infrastructure and business organisations summarised in sections 3 and 4 of this report. Indeed, the authors would argue that emergency responders, and the associated command and control procedures, should be considered as specialist critical infrastructure organisations where each emergency responder organisation integrates EEW and OEF systems into their disaster response plans.

The additional area that needs to be considered in great detail are the interrelationships between the different emergency responder organisation disaster management and response plans, and in particular ensuring that the plans of one emergency responder organisation do not inhibit other emergency responder organisations from performing their earthquake rapid response and recovery tasks in an optimal manner (Paton et al. *ibid*). To this end the command and control model (e.g. civic protection) should also ensure the effective integration of EEW and OEF systems into their communication and coordination procedures. The integration of EEW/OEF systems into emergency responder organisations' earthquake disaster procedures will be investigated during the TURNkey project, as will the wider role of the EEW/OEF systems to inform integrated emergency response planning.

6 REVIEW OF THE FACTORS AFFECTING ORGANISATION AND COMMUNITY RESILIENCE TO EARTHQUAKE EVENTS

This section of the report provides a brief overview of the factors affecting organisational and community resilience to earthquake events sufficient to inform the range and scope of questions/issues to be addressed in use-case interviews with end-user stakeholders in Tasks 1.3 and 1.4. A detailed analysis of the potential of EEW/OEF/RRE systems to improve organisational and community resilience to earthquake events, including the development of specific metrics to measure effectiveness, will be undertaken later in TURNkey WP5.

Jones (2016) reviewed the literature pertinent to improving the resilience of organisations and communities to earthquake events as part of the LIQUEFACT project. Although the LIQUEFACT project focused on identifying the impact that earthquake induced liquefaction (EIL) had on organisational and community resilience, the review of community resilience theory is applicable to any disaster stressor and as such directly applicable to the TURNkey project.

Jones (*ibid*) reviewed the ability of a range of conceptual and explanatory models to support the development of community and business tools to quantify the risks that EIL posed to organisations and communities, and to evaluate the potential benefits associated with a range of EIL mitigation actions. From this review Jones identified the range of resilience factors/characteristics and associated indicators/expectations shown in Table 6.1 (note: the original table was presented in LIQUEFACT Deliverable 1.1. and it has been updated here to include key publications since 2015).

Table 6.1: Characteristics/factors known to affect community resilience and how these are observed/expressed within a community (adapted from Jones, 2016)

Resilience Factor / Characteristic	Indicator / Expectations
Robustness	Damage avoidance in lifelines and critical infrastructure (transportation networks, residential housing stock, healthcare facilities, communication networks, commercial and manufacturing establishments etc.); Continuity of service provision; Continuity of functional systems performance; Avoidance of casualties; Avoidance / minimisation of economic losses.
Redundancy	Backup and/or duplicate systems; Backup or access to alternate resources to sustain operations (insurance, alternative sites, robust supply chains etc.); Alternative community logistics (food, water, power etc.); Untapped resources / contingency budgets.

Resourcefulness	Access to money; Information; Technology; Human resources; Household emergency plans; Business continuity plans; Diagnostic and damage detection systems; Contingency plans across stakeholder groups.
Rapidity	Disaster preparedness (organisational capacities, early warning systems, contingency planning, emergency response planning, etc.); Reduced time of recovery to return systems as close as possible to business as normal.
Personal Factors	Critical awareness; Self-efficacy; Sense of community; Outcome expectancy (positive or negative); Action coping and resource availability; Education and training; Psychological preparedness; Empowerment; Social norms; Trust; Personal responsibility; Social responsibility; Experience; Resources; Adaptive capacity; Cultural attitudes and motivations; Social networks; Property values; Livelihoods; Participation in recovery; Volunteering; Population Demographic; Mobility; Health; Homeownership; Income level; personal resilience of emergency responders.
Community Factors	Collective efficacy; Participation; Commitment; Information exchange; Social support; Decision making; Resource availability; Engagement; Leadership; Demographics; Sense of community; Community values-cohesion; Collective efficacy; Place attachment; Adaptive capacity; Local understanding of risk (hazard assessment, vulnerability assessment of critical infrastructure and lifelines, impact assessment, resource management, mitigation); Counselling services; Health and well-being services; Community organisations (e.g. faith based etc.); Employment; Business demographics; Poverty; Infrastructure exposure; Political engagement; Citizen disaster preparedness; Social capital; Cultural resources; Local food supplies; Efficient energy / water use; Detailed understanding of the interrelationships between communities, business and policy makers; Effective risk management strategies.
Institutional Factors	Empowerment; Trust; Resources; Mechanisms for community problem solving, Adaptive capacity, Participation in hazard reduction programmes; Hazard mitigation plans; Zoning and building standards; Emergency response plans; Interoperable communications; Continuity planning; Municipal finance / revenues; Jurisdictional coordination; Disaster aid experience; Population stability; Social connectivity; Housing stock profile; Shelter capacity; Effective continuity planning that recognises the need to understand the interdependencies between business needs, employees and local communities.
Governance Factors	Policy & planning; Legal and regulatory systems; Integration across time and scale; Leadership; Partnerships; Accountability; Sustainability.

Derived from: Ainuddin & Routray (2012); Becker et al. (2013); Boon et al. (2012); Bruneau et al. (2003); Tierney & Bruneau, (2007); Cutter et al. (2008); DPRAP³ (2013); GOAL⁴ (2012); Normandin et al. (2009); and Paton (2007) Cimellaro (2016); Paton (2017)

In addition to the above Tierney & Bruneau (2007) identified 4 dimensions/domains of resilience (technical, organisational, social, local and regional economies) that constitute a complex arrangement between organisational/community capacity and household's and business's ability to cope with disaster events. The idea that community resilience is a complex system comprising community groups

³ https://issuu.com/edwintoo/docs/cobra_conceptual_framework_and_meth

⁴ https://www.goalglobal.org/images/5101_HN_OP_006_11_Resilience_Toolkit_English_B02.pdf

households and businesses was also proposed by Boon et al. (2012); by Cavallo (2014); by Rovins (2017) and by Jones et al. (Hallett (ed), 2013). Bartolucci and Jones further developed the idea of community resilience as a complex system of systems model in the LIQUEFACT project (Bartolucci A. and Jones K. G., 2016) where he developed and EIL Resilience Assessment and Improvement Framework (RAIF) as the theoretical basis for evaluating the potential effectiveness of mitigation actions (physical or operational) to improve organisational and community resilience.

The RAIF (ibid) was developed from the Disaster Resilience of Place (DROP) model (Figure 6.1) proposed Cutter et al. (2008). The basis for Cutter et al.'s (ibid) conceptual model is the relationship between vulnerability and resilience. Cutter et al.'s model considers the inherent (antecedent conditions) vulnerability and resilience of existing communities (combination of natural systems, social system and the built environment) to a disaster event. The antecedent conditions interact with the hazard event characteristics to produce immediate effects. The event characteristics include frequency, duration, intensity, magnitude and rate of onset of the event that vary depending on the type of hazard and geographical location. The immediate effects of a disaster event are either reduced or amplified by the presence (or lack of) mitigation actions and coping responses. After any mitigation actions and/or coping strategies are implemented the hazard impact is realised. The impact of the event is moderated by the absorptive capacity of the local community. If the absorptive capacity of the local community is not exceeded then recovery is relatively quick. If the absorptive capacity is exceeded (either because the scale of the event is overwhelming or the coping responses are insufficient) then the community either adapts (through improvisation or social learning) and recovers relatively quickly, or does not adapt and recovery is much slower (or in extreme cases doesn't happen).

Figure 6.1: Schematic representation of the disaster resilience of place (DROP) model (source: Cutter et al., 2008)

The LIQUEFACT project reinterpreted Cutter et al.'s DROP model (ibid) and Jones' risk/resilience model (Hallett, 2012) to assess vulnerability, resilience, and mitigation options to support the development of business models to identify and prioritise mitigation actions to improve critical infrastructure and community resilience to EILD events. These business models and tools are shown mapped against Cutter et al.'s DROP model in Figure 6.2.

The LIQUEFACT community resilience assessment tool (used to model antecedent community resilience and the impact of the disaster on community resilience) uses a system of systems model of community resilience based on a customised version of the UNDRR disaster resilience scorecard for cities⁵. LIQUEFACT developed susceptibility and risk models to identify the specific EIL disaster event characteristics and coping responses; and vulnerability and resilience models were developed for critical infrastructure providers to assess the impact of an EIL disaster event would have on their ability to deliver the critical services that communities need as they recover from a disaster event. A range of mitigation interventions were identified to reduce the adverse impact of an EIL disaster event and a cost-benefit methodology was developed to support an options appraisal business model to prioritise the integration of suitable mitigation interventions into built asset management planning.

The business models and tools outlined above were integrated into a management framework (the RAIF – Figure 6.3) to provide detailed guidance to facilities/built asset managers and/or regional planners on the application of the theory (outlined in Figure 6.2) at the community or critical infrastructure built asset level. The RAIF will be reinterpreted in the TURNkey project (WP5) to identify a wider range of mitigation interventions and business tools/plans that could effectively integrate EEW/OEF/RRE systems into a general community resilience model.

Figure 6.2: LIQUEFACT tools mapped onto Cutter et al.'s DROP Model

⁵ for further details of the original scorecard see <https://www.unisdr.org/we/inform/publications/53349> for details of customised LIQUEFACT scorecard see LIQUEFACT Deliverable D5.4.

Figure 6.3: Resilience Assessment and Improvement Framework
(source: the LIQUEFACT project)

The idea that improvements to community resilience can be supported through the application of a range of resilience assessment and improvement framework's was further proposed by Paton and Johnstone (2017) in the book they edited on 'Disaster Resilience: An Integrated Approach 2nd Edition' where a range of authors presented 'state-of-the-art' reviews of the factors that affected community resilience to disaster events. The state-of-the-art reviews examined not only the challenges faced by individual stakeholders in preparing for and recovering from disaster events, but also explored the complex interrelationships between stakeholder groups that enhance or diminish the recovery process. Of particular relevance to the TURNkey project were the review of the state-of-the-art of the relationships between lifelines (referred to in this report as critical infrastructure) and urban resilience where Becker J. S. (Chapter 3) identified the importance of lifelines to support community recovery following a disaster event. In exploring these relationships Becker identified a process model for assessing the vulnerability of lifelines which included identifying their importance, vulnerability, interdependence, redundancy, and the impact of damage as precursors to identifying potential mitigation actions. In applying her process model Becker suggested a four phase workshop approach comprising 1) vulnerability assessments, 2) interdependence assessments, 3) mitigation options appraisals and 4) action planning for lifeline organisations to assess their current state of resilience to disaster events. The model developed by Becker is very similar in concept to that developed by Jones et al. in the LIQUEFACT project and which will form the basis for assessing the role that EEW/OEF/RRE have on improving community resilience to earthquake events in TURNkey WP5.

7 SWOT ANALYSIS

The final part of this report considers the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats of EEW/OEF systems to disaster risk reduction planning for improved community resilience to earthquake events (note: as described in section 5, RRE systems are considered a part of critical infrastructure providers in this section). The strengths/opportunities are presented in the form of perceived benefits (Table 7.1 and Table

7.2) whilst the weaknesses/threats are presented in the form of end-user performance requirements that the TURNkey FWCR platform must satisfy (Table 7.3).

The review of literature presented in Section 3 describing existing EEW systems and/or outlining the requirements of new systems identified the following actual/perceived benefits (strengths / opportunities):

- Public/Occupational safety;
- Improved mental preparedness/public health;
- Increased awareness/understanding amongst the general public and business organisations;
- A focus for community training;
- Activation of emergency and disaster management response plans;
- Utility (critical infrastructure and lifelines) control;
- On-site facility control;
- Mass transit/vehicle control;
- Industrial/commercial equipment/asset control;
- Large-scale and on-site facility access control;
- Post-event safety assessments/structural health monitoring of critical assets;
- Damage prediction zones for emergency responders and for the post-disaster recovery phase.

The above identify the strengths and opportunities of EEW systems to disaster risk reduction planning for improved community resilience to earthquake events. Table 7.1 provides an initial assessment of where these strengths and opportunities could be realised through the integration of EEW systems (as part of the TURNkey FWCR platform) into procedures and processes used to support each of the TURNkey end-user stakeholder groups. Table 7.1 also provides an initial assessment (based on the author's opinion) as to the potential significance (high, medium, low) of the use of the EEW aspects of the FWCR platform to overall community resilience.

Table 7.1: Strengths and opportunities of EEW systems to disaster risk reduction planning for improved community resilience to earthquake events

Benefits	Citizens	Emergency Responders	Critical Infrastructure Providers	Business Organisations
Public/Occupational safety	High	Low	Low	Low
Improved mental preparedness/public health;	High	Low	Low	Medium
Increased awareness / understanding amongst the general public and business organisations;	High	Low	Low	High
A focus for community training;	High	Low	Low	Low
Activation of emergency and disaster management response plans;	Low	Medium	High	High
Utility (critical infrastructure and lifelines) control;	Low	Medium	High	Low
On-site facility control;	Low	Medium	High	High
Mass transit/vehicle control;	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium
Industrial/commercial equipment/asset control;	Low	Low	High	High

Large-scale and on-site facility access control;	Low	Medium	High	High
Post-event safety assessments/structural health monitoring of critical assets;	Low	High	Medium	Medium
Damage prediction zones for emergency responders and for the post-disaster recovery phase.	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium

The strength of the relationships presented in Table 7.1 will be further explored in interviews with the different stakeholder groups across the TURNkey Testbeds.

The review of literature presented in Section 3 describing existing EEW systems and/or outlining the requirements of new systems identified the following end-user performance requirement that if not effectively addressed by the FWCR platform would constitute weaknesses and/or threats:

- Systems must be robust and reliable with metrics and outputs reflecting the different needs of different end-user stakeholder groups, including end-user attitudes to risk and tolerance for false-positive and false-negative alerts if organisations are to develop up-stream applications or integrate EEW alerts into their disaster management and business continuity planning.
- End-user applications and guidance need to reflect statutory and regulation frameworks within which different organisations operate and directly relate to critical system failure modes, including effective integration with on-site detection and alarm systems and interdependencies between different stakeholder organisations operating procedures.
- Systems must operate within a fair and equitable governance framework where all affected end-user stakeholder groups have confidence in the management and operational framework of the system, and in the procedures for addressing liability and consequences of false-positive and false-negative alerts.
- Funding must be available for the longer term operation and maintenance of the system if organisations are to invest in up-stream applications, including funding to support adequate training for different end-user stakeholder groups.
- Robust and effective communication channels must be integral to the EEW system and reflect IT security and firewall systems of different potential end-users. Communication protocols need to reflect the level of understanding of different stakeholder groups and present information in a format which is appropriate to different stakeholder groups.
- Systems must be designed to reflect the cultural and behavioural characteristics of the society within which they are located. Simply transposing a system from one cultural setting to another will not guarantee success.

The review of literature presented in Section 4 describing existing OEF systems and/or outlining the requirements of new systems identified the following actual/perceived benefits (strengths / opportunities):

- Loss estimates including damage to buildings, displaced residents, injuries and fatalities.
- Better informed national and local government planning (building codes and land zoning).
- Better informed emergency response plans (emergency responders and civic protection).
- Better informed disaster management/business continuity planning including supply chain logistics.

- Post-earthquake inspection priorities and reconstruction planning including cascading effects (e.g. landslides, liquefaction etc.).
- Increased public preparedness, reduced misinformation, and improved training scenarios
- Personal risk reduction.
- Better informed insurance industry and capital markets.

The above identify the strengths and opportunities of OEF systems to disaster risk reduction planning for improved community resilience to earthquake events. Table 7.2 provides an initial assessment of where these strengths and opportunities could be realised through the integration of OEF systems (as part of the TURNkey FWCR platform) into procedures and processes used to support each of the TURNkey end-user stakeholder groups. Table 7.2 also provides an initial assessment (based on the author's opinion) as to the potential significance (high, medium, low) of the use of the OEF aspects of the FWCR platform to overall community resilience.

Table 7.2: Strengths and opportunities of OEF systems to disaster risk reduction planning for improved community resilience to earthquake events

Benefits	Citizens	Emergency Responders	Critical Infrastructure Providers	Business Organisations
Loss estimates including damage to buildings, displaced residents, injuries and fatalities	Low	Medium	High	Medium
Better informed national and local government planning (building codes and land zoning)	High	Medium	Medium	Medium
Better informed emergency response plans (emergency responders and civic protection)	Medium	High	Low	Medium
Better informed disaster management/business continuity planning including supply chain logistics	Low	Medium	Medium	High
Post-earthquake inspection priorities and reconstruction planning including cascading effects (e.g. landslides, liquefaction etc.)	Medium	High	Medium	Medium
Increased public preparedness, reduced misinformation, and improved training scenarios	High	High	Medium	Medium
Personal risk reduction	High	Medium	Low	Low
Better informed insurance industry and capital markets	Medium	Low	Medium	Medium

The strength of the relationships presented in Table 7.2 will be further explored in interviews with the different stakeholder groups across the TURNkey Testbeds.

The review of literature presented in Section 4 describing existing OEF systems and/or outlining the requirements of new systems identified the following end-user performance requirements that if not effectively addressed by the FWCR platform would constitute weaknesses and/or threats:

- Forecasts must be robust and reliable with metrics and outputs reflecting the different needs of different end-user stakeholder groups (triggering thresholds), and include guidance that supports the development of up-stream applications including disaster management and business continuity plans. Metrics, outputs and guidance must also be available at a level of detail (granularity) that reflect the different needs of stakeholder groups.
- Guidance produced by OEF systems must reflect statutory and regulation frameworks within which different organisations operate.
- Forecasts must be complete, transparent, timely and policy neutral and operate within a fair and equitable governance framework. They must allow organisations to examine not only their vulnerability and resilience to earthquakes, but also that of their supply chains. This said, OEF systems must also consider the negative impact that a forecast could have on business organisations.
- Forecasts must effectively communicate uncertainties in both metrics and models and provide detailed guidance (including possible mitigation actions) and training on how to integrate OEF information into day-to-day decision-making and long-term built asset management planning.

Finally in this report, the EEW and OEF attributes of the FWCR platform are mapped against the contribution that each could contribute towards improved community resilience (Table 7.3). This mapping will inform the development of more detailed end-user use-cases to be developed later in WP1 and community resilience performance metrics to be developed later in WP5.

Table 7.3: The theoretical/potential relationship between EEW/OEF systems and the factors influencing community resilience to earthquake events

Resilience Factor / Characteristic	EEW systems	OEF systems
Robustness	Medium	Medium
Redundancy	Medium	High
Resourcefulness	High	Medium
Rapidity	Medium	Medium
Personal Factors	High	Medium
Community Factors	Medium	Medium
Institutional Factors	Medium	High
Governance Factors	Medium	Medium

The strength of the relationships presented in Table 7.3 will be further explored in interviews with the different stakeholder groups across the TURNkey Testbeds.

8 SUMMARY AND NEXT STEPS

This report has reviewed the benefits/challenges associated with EEW, OEF and RRE systems and mapped these against a brief overview of the theory of community resilience to identify how these benefits/challenges inform the future development of the TURNkey FWCR platform.

The next steps for WP1 (Tasks 1.3 and 1.4) are to develop a greater understanding of how the potential benefits derived from EEW, OEF, and RRE systems can be realised by individual citizens, emergency

responders, critical infrastructure providers and business organisations. This will include validating the strength of the proposed relationships shown in Tables 7.1 and 7.2 with members of the TURNkey consortium and stakeholder groups in selected TURNkey testbeds and developing specific end-user use cases that describe specific application of the FWCR platform to improved disaster risk reduction and community resilience.

The next steps for WP5 are to further explore and expand on the potential relationships between EEW/OEF systems and their potential to improve community resilience to earthquake events.

The review presented in the report should be considered a work in progress which will be amended and modified throughout the TURNkey project to reflect emerging issues identified through the participatory action research programme.

9 REFERENCES

Auclair, S., Goula, X., Jara, J. A., and Colom, Y. (2014) 'Feasibility and interest in earthquake early warning systems for areas of moderate seismicity: case study for the Pyrenees, *Pure Applied Geophysics*, DOI: 10.1007/s0024-014-0957-x

Allen, R. M., Gasparini, P., Kamigaichi, O. and Böse, M. (2009) 'The Status of Earthquake Early Warning around the World: An Introductory Overview' *Seismological Research Letters* 80 (5): 682-693. <https://doi.org/10.1785/gssrl.80.5.682>

Ainuddin, S. and Routray, J., K. (2012) 'Earthquake hazards and community resilience in Baluchistan' *Natural Hazards*, vol 63, pp 909-937. DOI: 10.007/s11069-012-0201

Becker, J., McBride, S. and Paton, D. (2013) 'Improving community resilience in the Hawke's Bay: A review of resilience research, and current public education, communication and resilience strategies, GNS Science Report 2013/38

Becker, J. S. (2019) 'The potential for earthquake early warning in New Zealand: investigating the social benefits', QuakeCoRE Seminar 17 May 2019

Becker, J. S., Potter, S. H., McBride, S. K., Wien, A. Doyle, E. E. H. and Paton, D. (2019) 'When the earth doesn't stop shaking: how experiences over time influenced information needs, communication, and interpretation of after-shock information during the Canterbury earthquake sequence, New Zealand', *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 34, pp 397-411
DOI: 10.1016/j.ijdrr.2018.12.009

Becker, J., S., Potter, S. and Doyle, E. E. E. (2015) 'After-shock communication during the Canterbury earthquakes, New Zealand: implications for response and recovery in the built environment', paper presented at the New Zealand Society of earthquake engineering proceedings, Rotorua, New Zealand. Available at http://www.nzsee.org.nz/db/2015/Papers/O-52_Becker.pdf Accessed on 13/11/2019

Becker, J. S., Paton, D., Johnston, D. M. and Ronan, K. R. (2012) 'A model of household preparedness for earthquakes: how individuals make meaning of earthquake information and how this influences preparedness', *Natural Hazards*, 64, pp 107-137

Boon, J., Cottrell, A., King, D., and Stevenson, J. M. (2012) 'Bronfenbrenner's bioecological theory for modelling community resilience to natural disasters'. *Natural Hazards*, vol 60, pp 381-408
DOI: 10.1007/s11069-011-0021-4

Bose, R., Allen, R., Brown, H., Gua, G., Fischer, E., Hauksson, E., Heaten, T., Hellweg, M., Liukis, M., Neuhauser, P., Maechling, P., Solanki, K., Vinci, M., Hense, I., Khainovski, O., Kuyuk, S., Carpio, M., Meier, M. and Jordan, T. (2013) 'CISN SharkAlert: an earthquake early warning demonstration system for California', Available at https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-642-12233-0_3 Accessed on 28/11/2019

Bruneau, M., Chang, S. E., Eguchi, R. T., Lee, G. C., O'Rourke, T. D., Reinhorn, A. M., Shinozuka, M., Tierney, K., Wallace, W. A. and von Winterfeldt, D. (2003) 'A Framework to Quantitatively Assess and Enhance the Seismic Resilience of Communities', *Earthquake Spectra*: November 2003, Vol. 19, No. 4, pp. 733-752

Cauzzi, C., Behr, Y., le Guenan, T., Douglas, J., Auclair, S., Woessner, J., Clinto, J. and Wiemer (2016), 'Earthquake early warning and operational earthquake forecasting as real-time hazard information to mitigate seismic risk at nuclear facilities', *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering*, 14 pp 2495-2512. DOI: 10.1007/s10518-016-9864-0

Cavallo, A. (2014) 'Integrating disaster preparedness and resilience: a complex approach using a system of systems', *Australian Journal of Emergency Management*, Vol 29, No 3, pp 46-51

Cimellaro G. P. (2016) 'Urban resilience for emergency response and recovery', Springer, ISBN 978-3-319-30656-8

Cutter, S. L., Barnes, L., Berry, M., Burton, C., Evans, E., Tate E., & Webb J. (2008) 'A place-based model for understanding community resilience to natural disasters', *Global Environmental Change*, Vol 18, pp598-606

Daniell, J. E., Khazai, B., Wenzel, F. and Vervaeck, A. (2012) The worldwide economic impact of historic earthquakes'. Proceedings of the fifteenth world conference on earthquake engineering, Lisbon, Portugal, 2012. Available online at: http://www.iitk.ac.in/nicee/wcee/article/WCEE2012_2038.pdf Accessed on 29/10/2019

Doocy S, Daniels A, Packer C, Dick A, Kirsch TD. The Human Impact of Earthquakes: a Historical Review of Events 1980-2009 and Systematic Literature Review. *PLOS Currents Disasters*. 2013 Apr 16 . Edition 1. DOI: 10.1371/currents.dis.67bd14fe457f1db0b5433a8ee20fb833

DOI. K. (2011) 'The operation and performance of earthquake early warnings by the Japan metrological agency', *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*, 31, pp 119-126
DOI:10.1016/j.soildyn.2010.06.009

Douglas, J., Woo, G., Auclair, S. and Le Guenan, T. (2012) 'Critical review of participatory decision-making in fields other than earthquake risk reduction. Final report', BRGM/RP-61480-FR. Availableonline at : <https://www.brgm.eu/scientific-output/public-reports/public-reports> Accessed on 28/11/2019

Dunn, P. T., Ahn, A. Y. E., Bostom, A. and Vidale (2016) 'perception of earthquake early warnings on the U.S. West Coast', *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 20, pp 112-122

ePACT available at: <https://www.epactnetwork.com/corp/blog/geographical-breakdown-natural-disasters-europe/>. Accessed on 29/10/2019

FEMA. (2009) 'BCA Reference Guide' available online at http://www.fema.gov/media-library-data/20130726-1736-25045-7076/bca_reference_guide.pdf. Accessed on 28/11/2019

Field, E. W., Jordan, T. H., Jones, L. M., Michael, A. J., Blanpied, M. L., And other workshop participants, (2016) 'The potential uses of operational earthquake forecasting', *seismological Research Letters*, volume 87, number 2A, March/April 2016, pp 313-321. DOI: 10.1785/0220150174

Goltz, J. D. (2014) 'Social and behavioural aspects of earthquake early warning', presentation at the National Earthquake Program Managers Meetings, Denver, 2014. Available online at <https://www.wsspc.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/06/5-EEW-Training-Jim-Goltz.pdf> Accessed on 28/11/2019

Hallett, S. (Editor) (2013) *Community Resilience to Extreme Weather – the CREW Project: Final Report*. 110pp. www.extreme-weather-impacts.net. Available online https://arcc.ouce.ox.ac.uk/wp-content/pdfs/CREW_Final_Report.pdf Accessed on 22/11/2019

Hamilton et al. (2011) 'National earthquake resilience: research, implementation, and outreach', National Academies Press, Washington DC. ISBN: 978-0-309-18677-3. Available online at <https://www.nehrp.gov/pdf/NRC2011.pdf> Accessed on 28/11/2019

Jones, K., Morga, M., Wanigarathna, N., Pascale, F. and Yarovaya, L. (2019) Cost-benefit analysis of liquefaction mitigation strategies. In: *IABSE Symposium 2019 Guimarães - Towards a Resilient Built Environment - Risk and Asset Management*, Guimarães, Portugal

Jones K. (2016) 'The Challenge to Improve Community Resilience to EILD Events: A Review of Theory', LIQUEFACT Project Deliverable 1.1. Available at: <https://zenodo.org/record/1342684#.XVu1J0xFzIU>

Johnson, L. A., Rabinovici, S., Kang, G. S. and Mahin, S. A. (2016) 'California Earthquake Early Warning System Benefit Study', CSSC publication 16-04, PEER report number 2016/06, July 29, 2016 Available online at: https://peer.berkeley.edu/sites/default/files/caoes-cssc1604-peer201606-caeews-benefits-study_final_8.31.16.pdf Accessed on 28/11/2019

Jordan, T. H., Chen, Y., Gasparini, P., Madariaga, R., Main, I., Marzocchi, W., Papadopoulos, G., Sobolev, G., Yamaoka, K. and Zschau, J. (2011) 'OPERATIONAL EARTHQUAKE FORECASTING State of Knowledge and Guidelines for Utilization', Report by the International Commission on Earthquake Forecasting for Civil Protection, available online at https://www.earth-prints.org/bitstream/2122/7442/1/AG_jordan_etal_11.pdf Accessed on 28/11/2019

Lieberman, C. (2015) 'The benefits and costs of an earthquake early warning system in Washington State', *the Evans School Review*, 5, pp121-136. Available at <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/23f2/8f77a1674f914dc5865cff7c871741fc5509.pdf>

Bartolucci, A. and Jones, K. (2016) 'EILD Risk: Resilience Assessment and Improvement Framework', LIQUEFACT Project Deliverable 1.3. Available at: <https://zenodo.org/record/1342687#.XVu1ckxFzIU>

Minson, S. E., Meier, M., Baltay, A. S., Nanks, T. C. and Cochran, E. S. (2017), 'The limits of earthquake early warning: timeliness of ground motion estimates', *Science Advances*, 4, (3), DOI: 10.1126/sciadv.aag0504

Nakayachi, K., Becker, J. S., Potter, S. H. and Dixon, M. (2019) 'Residents' reactions to earthquake early warnings in Japan', *Risk Analysis*, DOI: 10.1111/risa.13306

Nakamura, Y., Saita, and Satao T. (2011) 'on an earthquake early warning system (EEW) and its applications', *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*, 31, pp 127-136
DOI:10.1016/j.soildyn.2010.04.012

Normandin, J. M., Therrien, M. C. and Tanguay, G., A. (2009) 'City strengths in times of turbulence: strategic resilience indicators' available online at:
http://s3.amazonaws.com/academia.edu.documents/43744799/CITY_STRENGTH_IN_TIMES_OF_TURBULANCE_STR20160315-24110-1hfs gul.pdf?AWSAccessKeyId=AKIAJ56TQJRTWSMTNPEA&Expires=1469702033&Signature=OYMsIgl3hYcTWqdSawesyIoKFbc%3D&response-content-disposition=inline%3B%20filename%3DCity_Strength_in_Times_of_Turbulence_Str.pdf

Pagano, L. and Sica, S. (2013) 'Earthquake early warning for earth dams: concepts and objectives', *Natural Hazards*, 66, pp 303 – 318, DOI: 10.1007/s11069-012-0486-9

Paton, D (2007) 'Measuring and monitoring resilience in Auckland', GNS Science Report 2007/18

Paton, D., Moss, S., Violanti, J., De Leon, J. and Morrissey, H. (2017) 'Chapter 17 of DISASTER RESILIENCE An Integrated Approach'.2nd Edition', Paton, D. and Johnstone, D. Editors, Charles C Thomas Publisher, ISBN: ISBN 978-0-398-09169-9

Rainieri, C., Fabbrocino, G. and Cosenza E. (2010) 'Integrated seismic early warning and structural health monitoring of critical civil infrastructures in seismically prone areas', *Structural Health Monitoring*, 10, (3), DOI: 10.1177/1475921710373296

Rovins, J. (2017) 'Chapter 21 17 of DISASTER RESILIENCE An Integrated Approach'.2nd Edition', Paton, D. and Johnstone, D. Editors, Charles C Thomas Publisher, ISBN: ISBN 978-0-398-09169-9

Satriano, C., Wu, Y., Zollo, A. and Kanamori (2011) 'Earthquake early warning: concepts, methods and physical grounds', *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*, 31, pp 106-118 DOI: 10.1016/j.soildyn.2010.07.007

Strauss, J. A. and Allen, R. M. (2016) 'Benefits and costs of earthquake early warning', *Seismological Research Letters*, 87, 3, pp 772, DOI: 10.1785/0220150149

Tierney, K. & Bruneau, M. (2007) 'Conceptualizing and Measuring Resilience: A key to Disaster Loss Reduction', TR News 250, May-June 2007

TURNkey Grant Agreement, 2019, unpublished

Wenzel, F., Baur, M., Fiedrich, F., Ionescu, C. and Oncescu, C. (2001) 'Potential earthquake early warning systems', *Natural Hazards*, 23, pp 407-416

Woo G., Marzocchi W. (2014) Operational Earthquake Forecasting and Decision-Making. In: Wenzel F., Zschau J. (eds) Early Warning for Geological Disasters. Advanced Technologies in Earth Sciences. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. ISBN 978-3-642-12232-3

Gobbato, M., Shome, N. and Woo, G. (2017) 'The cost effectiveness of a West Coast earthquake early warning system', 16th World Conference on Earthquake Engineering (WCEE 2017), Santiago, Chile 9-13 January 2017, Vol 2, pp1084-1093

Yamasaki, E. (2011) 'What we can learn from Japan's earthquake early warning system', Momentum, Vol 1, Issue 1, Available online at https://repository.upenn.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1022&=&context=momentum&=&sei-redir=1&referer=https%253A%252F%252Fscholar.google.com%252Fscholar%253Fhl%253Den%2526as_sdt%253D0%25252C5%2526q%253DYamasaki%25252C%252BE.%252B%2525282011%252529%252B%2525E2%252580%252598What%252Bwe%252Bcan%252Blearn%252Bfrom%252BJapan%252527s%252Bearthquake%252Bearly%252Bwarning%252Bsystem%2525E2%252580%252599%2526btnG%253D#search=%22Yamasaki%2C%20E.%20%282011%29%20%2E%20%80%98What%20can%20learn%20from%20Japans%20earthquake%20early%20warning%20system%E2%80%99%22
 Accessed on 28/11/2019

Yamazaki, F. (2003), 'Early Warning Systems for Mitigation of Earthquake-Related Technological Risks', In: Zschau J., Küppers, A. (eds) Early Warning Systems for Natural Disaster Reduction. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg